

Cyclisation of 4-(1'-benzoylamino-4'-anthraquinonylamino) Benzanthrone

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Manuscript received 28 July 1975; accepted 14 May 1976

Cyclisation of 4-(1'-benzoylamino-4'-anthraquinonylamino)-Benzanthrone is stated to yield a grey dye by bromination in chlorosulphonic acid and the cyclisation to acridine is assumed. The structure of the cyclised compound has been confirmed by oxidation, and a mechanism of cyclisation involving a radical cation intermediate is proposed.

4-(1'-benzoylamino-4'-anthraquinonylamino) Benzanthrone (I) was prepared by the reaction of benzanthrone (II) with 1-amino-4-benzamido-anthraquinone(III) using dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and potassium hydroxide¹. The structure of this product has been assigned on the basis of oxidation studies which yielded (IV) and its cyclisation to the dye. (I) is stated to cyclise to (V), an olive green dye², with chlorosulphonic acid during bromination. The structure of the cyclised product requires confirmation.

Cyclisation of (I) could be achieved with chlorosulphonic acid. The analysis of the cyclised product indicated that the reaction involved cyclodehydrogenation. The colour of the dye was similar to that of its isomer (VI). Oxidation of the cyclised product gave (VII) which indicated that the cyclisation had taken place in the 3-position of benzanthrone. The oxidation product dyed cotton pink from brown red alkaline dithionite vat. This easy cyclisation in the presence of a benzoylamino group indicated that it was similar to the cyclisation of 1,1'-dianthrimides (VIII) with the benzoylamino groups in 4,4'-, 4,5'-or 5,5'-positions. Venkataraman³ has recently suggested a mechanism involving a radical cation intermediate for the latter reaction.

Weiss⁴ has proposed a radical mechanism for the formation of 3,3'-dibenzanthronyl (IX) by the reaction of benzanthrone with sulphuric acid and an oxidising agent. Free radical formation in benzanthrone with concentrated sulphuric acid has been indicated by polarographic⁵ and magnetic susceptibility studies⁶. So the mechanism of the formation of the dye (V) can be visualised as shown in the Scheme. The function of a benzoylamino group in an anthrimide is to favour the protonation of the amide CO group. The -NH group in the anthrimide and the CO group in benzanthrone protonate in sulphuric acid solution giving the structure (X). Enolisation of the amide group, protonation of the adjacent quinone carbonyl, and disproportionation to the cationic structure gives (XI). Loss of 2H.

yields (XII) involving radical cations which rearrange to (XIII), and cyclisation takes place to yield (XIV.)

The cyclised dye (V) is obtained by subsequent oxidation by sulphuric acid.

SCHEME

The benzoylamino group in an aminoanthraquinonyl nucleus favours the formation of a radical cation intermediate and its stability; in its absence such an intermediate even if it is formed is not stable. Hence the cyclisation of 4-(1'-anthraquinonylamino) benzanthrone does not involve such an intermediate.

The spectral characteristics of (I) and (V) are given below.

Compound	λ max in sulphuric acid in nm	C=O region— ν — cm^{-1}	ir—C—C region— cm^{-1}
(I)	240, 278, 340, 472–492, 523	1650	1575, 1505.
(V)	261, 285, 338, 375–400, 428, 445, 515.	1670	1570, 1542, 1520.

No conclusions can be drawn from the ultra violet spectral data. Differentiation by infra red in the C=O region is not applicable to dyes containing benzoylamino groups; in the C—C stretch region, the cyclised product shows more bands than the uncyclised product confirming Shah's observation in similar compounds.⁷

Experimental

1-Amino-4-benzoylamino-anthraquinone (III)

The commercial intermediate (from Schuchardt Munchen, West Germany) was reddish violet. Crystallisation from nitrobenzene gave fine violet needles, m.p. 287° (lit.⁸, m.p. 278°), (Found : C, 73.6; H, 3.9; N, 8.1%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$, C, 73.7; H, 4.1; N, 8.2%).

4-(1'-benzoylamino-4'-anthraquinonylamino) Benzanthrone (I)

Benzanthrone (3 g.), 1-amino-4-benzoylamino-anthraquinone (2 g.), dimethyl sulphoxide (25 ml), powdered potassium hydroxide (9 g.) were stirred at room temperature for 6 hr. The greyish green product was collected after dilution with water. Crystallisation from nitrobenzene gave grayish green needles (2.5 g) not melting upto 300°. It was analysed for the formula (I). (Found : C, 80.0; H, 4.2; N, 5.0%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$, C, 80.0; H, 3.9; N, 4.9%. λ_{max} in sulphuric acid at 240, 278, 340, 472–492, 523 nm. Infra red at 1650 cm^{-1} in C=O region and 1505 and 1575 cm^{-1} in the C—C stretch region).

Oxidation of (I)

(I) (2 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) and the mixture was refluxed. To it was added chromium trioxide (8 g.) in water (40 ml) and acetic acid (60 ml) dropwise. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hr more and then diluted with water (3 l.) and kept overnight. The red precipitate which separated was collected. yield; 0.6 g. It was insoluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and liquor ammonia. Crystallisation of the product from *o*-dichlorobenzene gave red needles.

The red product (0.5 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (15 ml) and stirred at 100° for 1 hr. The red precipitate which separated on dilution with water, was collected. Crystallisation from *o*-dichlorobenzene gave red needles. It was analysed for the formula (IV). Found : C, 70.9; H, 3.3; N, 5.4%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$, C, 71.3; H, 3.3; N, 5.7%). It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with yellow solution.

Cyclisation of (I)

The anthrimide (I) was cyclised with chlorosulphonic acid at room temperature. A solution of (I) (1 g.) in chlorosulphonic acid (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 4 hr. The mixture was diluted with concentrated sulphuric acid and then poured over crushed ice. The green precipitate which separated was collected. Crystallisation from nitrobenzene gave green needles. It was analysed for

(V). (Found : C, 80.6; H, 3.2; N, 4.9%. Calc. for $C_{38}H_{20}N_2O_4$, C, 80.3; H, 3.5; N, 4.9%). λ_{max} in sulphuric acid at 261, 285, 338, 385-395, 445, and 515 nm. Infra red at 1630 and 1670 cm^{-1} in C=O region, and 1520, 1542 and 1570 cm^{-1} in C-C stretch region). It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with violet colour which changed to blue at 100°. The product dyed cotton green from a blue alkaline dithionite vat.

Oxidation of (V)

(V) was oxidised in a manner similar to that described for the oxidation of (I). The brick red precipitate were collected. Crystallisation from dimethyl formamide gave brick red micro crystals which were analysed for the formula (VII). (Found : C, 75.0; H, 3.0; N, 4.7%. Calc. for $C_{38}H_{18}N_2O_8$; C, 75.3; H, 3.2; N, 4.9%). It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with reddish yellow colour. It dyed cotton yellowish pink from a brown alkaline dithionite vat.

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